

Data Based Controller Design for PMDC Motor Setup using System Identification

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Abstract

Identification or first principle-based processes of the modelling have turned very difficult. The conventional control theory-based modelling of systems has thus become almost impractical because of this reason. The research proposes the development of a microcontroller-based model-free control system setup for a permanent magnet DC (PMDC) motor. After designing the motor control drive setup, the data is acquired using serial communication protocol and further sent to the MATLAB whereupon the serial data is used to identify the system. System identification toolbox is used to identify the transfer function of the plant setup using the serial data collected from the microcontroller. The data driven controller could be directly designed based on time response data using control algorithms based on proportional-integral-derivative (PID) controllers which are completely free of complex mathematical models. The setup is totally low cost for laboratory use compared to the commercially available setups and can be used to perform several complex control system experiments such as ball beam, ball on the wheel and inverted pendulum, etc. System identification toolbox is used to identify the transfer function of the plant setup using the serial data collected from the microcontroller.

Keywords: System identification, PMDC motor, PID controller, Data driven control, Controller design.

1. Introduction

The model based control developed after the introduction of the optimal control with the state space model by [1], giving rise to modern control theory. model based control found its applications in many fields, particularly in fields with availability of accurate models like aeronautical engineering, automotive and defence developments. Both linear and non-linear systems are dealt by the model based control theory. The controller design of complex systems is very cumbersome even if the physical model of the complex system is available [2]. Methodologies like robust control, design based on linear quadratic regulator and pole-zero placement are used for the designing of linear systems. While as methodologies like backstepping controller design, Lyapunov controller design and linearization using feedback are employed for the controller design of the non-linear systems. All above mentioned design strategies are included in the modern control theory. The identification of the plant model is the primary step of the modern control theory. The controller is then designed based on the model assuming that the model identified represents the exact dynamics of the system under consideration. The identification and the modelling are therefore essential to the model based control theory. However, this approach leads to erroneous controller design if there is difference in actual plant dynamics and the dynamics represented by the identified model.

Modelling is an approximation process, there could always be an error associated with it whether it is done through system identification from data or even by first principle method. This error appears due to existence of some unmodelled system dynamics. These unmodelled dynamics further lead to the less robustness of the system[3]–[5]. First principle based modelling and system identification are very limited especially regarding the explicit error quantification. Dearth of practical uncertainty and inadequate descriptions are the main hurdles in the applicability of the first principle based controller design [5], [6].

Figure 1. Schematic algorithm of model based control theory

First principle based controller design is assumed on certainty equivalence principle. If there is mismatch between assumed model and the actual plant model, the model based controller approach might not provide the accurate results. Thus, this model based controller design approach using an inaccurate model for designing a controller can cause instability of the whole system or its undesired performance. Undesired close-loop performance could be a result of small random errors [7]. If incorrect assumptions are made, the results obtained by the model based control theory could not be valuable every time even when the accurate model is available. Figure 1 describes the schematic algorithm of model based control theory. It can be seen that in the model based control theory, the assumptions and the model itself are both the starting and the end points of the of the controller design. However, there is difference between the model obtained using the assumptions and the controlled plant, however this difference disappears while designing the controller.

The production process in various industrial fields like electric transmission, electronic appliances, transportation have gone through substantial changes with the development of new technologies, thus making their modelling process more complex. Hence, the first principle based modelling process for such systems becomes cumbersome. The model based control theory for the controller design in these industries becomes almost impractical.

Our modern industries rely heavily on huge amounts of data. This historical data is used by the industries for various state estimations, stability analysis, fault prediction, decision making and prediction of various output parameters. The analysis could be done either offline or in real time, depending upon the type and requirement of controller. This kind of requirement in the industry led to the development and application of data driven controller design theory [8]. This data driven control theory is also called as data based control theory, however, data based control implicitly represents an open loop system where the data is used at the initial stage only while the former suggests the process is a feedback system with both the initial and final points depending on data [9].

Figure 2 describes the schematic algorithm of data driven control theory The controller design using either real time or offline data based on the data driven control theory could be ensured by making use of computational analysis after taking into account some considerable assumptions [10].

Figure 2. Schematic algorithm of data driven control theory

This paper proposes the development of a control setup for permanent magnet DC motor which could be used for laboratory applications. By applying the standard test signals and acquiring the corresponding output to the input test signals from the PMDC motor setup, the system transfer function is identified by system identification toolbox of Matlab. System identification involves the process of building the transfer function model from the input-output data. Further, the data driven controller could be directly designed based on identified model using control algorithms.

2. Permanent Magnet DC Motor Setup

The proposed data driven control design is devised for an experimental controller setup which consists broadly of a permanent magnet DC motor, a microcontroller, H-bridge and a computer. The block diagram of the setup is given in the Figure 3. The DC motor used in the setup is a 20 watt Maxon motor with an optical shaft encoder. The specifications of the Maxon motor used are given in Table I. A 1000 CPR optical differential encoder with 3 channels attached to the motor is used to measure the position and speed of the motor. The encoder has two channels X & Y which carry square pulses in quadrature to each other. These pulses are processed in the microcontroller to calculate the motor speed, thus forming the feedback of the setup.

Figure 3. Block diagram of the PMDC motor setup

Table 1. Specifications of the Maxon motor

Specification	Value
Rated voltage	42 V
Speed at zero load	11100 rpm
Current at zero load	25.2 mA
Rated speed	9920 rpm
Maximum permissible speed	11000 rpm
Terminal resistance	52.9 Ω
Starting current	7940 Ma

Speed constant	268 rpm/V
Torque constant	35.6 mNm/A
Terminal inductance	0.551 mH
Rotor inertia	10.6 gcm ²

Microcontroller receives the position data and then sends it to the Matlab via RS232 protocol wherein this data is used to identify the transfer function of the permanent magnet DC motor. The microcontroller used in this setup is Arduino Uno which based on the 8-bit AVR ATmega328P. The programming for this Arduino Uno is performed using Arduino IDE software.

3. Decoding for Position and Voltage Management

The encoder consists of a non-transparent disk with successive equally spaced window like slits along the circumference of the disk. The opaque itself is coupled with shaft of the DC motor. Light is projected on to the disk along these slits called a track. On the backside of the disk lies a series of photosensors that detects the incoming through a slit and detects the light interruptions between slits. There is usually one photo sensor for one track of slits and could consist of a PV cell, a photo transistor or a photodiode. A train of voltage pulses is developed by the photosensors after interruptions of light is detected by them when light hits the opaque areas of the disk. The values of angular position as well as the angular velocity could be calculated from the same train of voltage pulses.

The measurement of angular positions and the angular velocities are carried to the Arduino board directly via a bus of pins. The angular position could be measured from the setup using following two decoding schemes:

3.1. X2 decoding

In X2 decoding, both rising and falling edges of pulse of channel A are monitored, therefore making the number of pulses twice the actual number of pulses in order to improve the resolution. Therefore, for optical encoder with 1000 PPR, the X2 decoding scheme will give 2000 counts for one revolution. Figure 4 represents the output of encoder having two channels X and Y.

Figure 4. Output of encoder having two channels X and Y

3.2. X4 decoding

In X4 decoding, the rising and falling edges of pulse of both channel X and channel Y are monitored, therefore making the number of pulses four times the actual number of pulses in order to improve the resolution. Hence, for optical encoder with 1000 PPR, the X2 decoding scheme will give 4000 counts for one revolution. Figure 5 represents the output of encoder having two channels X and Y, using X4 decoding scheme. Table II gives the truth table of the output using X4 decoding.

Figure 5. Output of encoder having two channels X and Y

Table 2. Truth table of the output using X4 decoding

State	X	Y	Direction
1	0	0	CCW
2	0	1	CW
3	1	0	CW
4	1	1	CCW

The angular velocity in both X2 decoding and X4 decoding is measured in counts per second. The output values of angular position and velocity are then represented in terms of PWM signals.

4. System Identification

The system identification toolbox is provided in the Matlab software and comes with wide range of functions and tools along with interactive blocks for the visualisation and modelling of real world

dynamic systems. The discrete and continuous transfer functions, state space models or process models are identified by feeding the output and input data in frequency domain and time domain.

The estimation of input data is done on time domain data using the time identified transfer function estimation. The transfer function for the given set up retrieved from system identification is given in equation 1.

$$G = \frac{0.0011827}{s^2 + 0.08528s + 0.002312} \quad (1)$$

Estimation – 89.57% (stability enforced)

5. Results

The research was able to determine the number of counts per revolution. One complete revolution produces 1000 pulses. By attaching the interrupt at rising state on index pulse the counter was reset after every revolution. The motor that we have used in setup has a gear train coupled with it having a reduction ratio of 19:1 i.e., for each complete revolution of the shaft there are 19 complete revolutions on encoder side. Using X2 decoding we were able to determine the direction (whether clockwise or counter-clockwise) using the Arduino sketch. The count was found to be increasing for clockwise direction and decreasing for counter-clockwise direction.

Calculation of the angular position from number of counts using X2 decoding is given in the equation 2.

$$2\pi = 2000 \text{ counts}$$
$$1 \text{ count} = \frac{\pi}{1000} \text{ rad} \quad (2)$$

Similarly, calculation of the angular position from number of counts using X4 decoding is given in the equation 3.

$$2\pi = 4000 \text{ counts}$$
$$1 \text{ count} = \frac{\pi}{2000} \text{ rad} \quad (3)$$

The system transfer function is identified by system identification toolbox of Matlab. System identification involves the process of building the transfer function model from the input-output data. The transfer function for the given set up retrieved from system identification is already given in equation 1.

$$G = \frac{0.0011827}{s^2 + 0.08528s + 0.002312}$$

The pole-zero plot of the plant transfer function is given in the Figure 6. This plot clearly shows that the system has two complex poles located in the left half plane and hence represents a stable

system. The location of these poles can be easily changed by different control methods to obtain the desired result. Figure 7 represents the root-locus of the plant model obtained using system identification toolbox. From the obtained transfer function, it is clear that there are two poles with location given by pole-zero plot and two zeroes at infinity which results in two root locus branches ending at infinity. Figure 8 represents the step response of the given transfer function from which different parameters like rise time, delay time and peak time can be determined. The curve fitting of the obtained transfer function is given in the Figure 9.

Figure 6. Pole-zero plot of the plant transfer function

Figure 7. Root-locus of the plant model

Figure 8. Step response of the obtained transfer function

Figure 9. Curve fitting of the given obtained transfer function

6. Conclusion

In this paper an attempt was made to develop a permanent magnet DC motor control setup for laboratory applications. An H-bridge was used to control the input to the motor in both the directions. Microcontroller was used for capturing the data from the optical encoder of the Maxon motor and then this data was sent to Matlab where further processing like position and velocity calculations were performed. This data was then loaded to the system identification toolbox wherein the transfer function of the plant was obtained. The total cost on this setup was much less than the cost of off-the shelf control setups. From this transfer function model different control system experiments like ball on beam, inverted pendulum etc. can be performed.

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